

Liouville - Continuity Equation Approach to Deriving the Schrodinger Equation

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There have been numerous papers in the literature which derive the Schrodinger equation from a classical Liouville equation together with a classical continuity one. These use classical density $d(x,t)$ and $p(x,t)$ where p is momentum as well as d/dt partial and grad partial. We focus on a recent one (1).

It seems that all of these Liouville approaches use the notion of $p(x,t) = d/dx S(x,t)$ in the continuity equation. Furthermore, they all lead to a $-dS/dt$ partial term in an energy conservation equation, which yields E for a bound state. (We ultimately conclude that these assumptions are equivalent to quantum mechanics for a free particle and that using conservation of average energy one may bypass the Liouville-continuity equations.)

At the same time, various approaches (including (1)) present a set of statistical ideas required to create an expression for average kinetic energy using classical density $d(x,t)$.

We suggest, however, that $p=d/dx$ partial $S(x,t)$ and $E= -d/dt$ partial $S(x,t)$ really mean in the bound state case the use of the function $-Et+px$ which is a Lorentz invariant and both the relativistic and nonrelativistic classical action of a free particle for $v=x/t$. Given that one deals with statistical equations, $p \exp(-iEt+ipx) / \exp(-iEt+ipx)$ may be thought of as the average of p for a free particle. The operator id/dt partial returns E and $-id/dx$ partial p . In general, these approaches are applied to a bound state where E is the bound energy and p , the cm momentum (which is usually 0). If $\exp(-iEt+ipx)$, however, represents the center of mass, it equally represents a free particle.

Following these ideas, one should consider writing $KE_{ave}(x) = \{ \text{Sum over } p \ p^2/2m \ a(p)\exp(ipx) \} / \{ \text{Sum over } a(p)\exp(ipx) \}$ for the case of a potential $V(x)$. This then leads to $-1/2m \ d/dx \ d/dx \ W/W$ where $W= \text{Sum over } p \ a(p)\exp(-ipx)$, but also $W(x)W(x)= d(x,t)$. In particular, these approaches use $W \exp(i S(x,t))$ such that this multiplied by its complex conjugate yields $d(x,t)$. We also note that in the free particle case $d(x,t)=1$ and $\exp(iS(x,t))$ multiplied by its conjugate yields the classical density.

Thus, we argue that no special statistical considerations are needed in a Liouville-continuity equation approach as considering $\exp(-iEt+ipx)$ as a probability already creates the quantum result together with conservation of energy.

Approach of (1)

For many years, there have been Liouville-continuity equation classical approaches in the literature using $d(x,t)$ (classical density) to derive the Schrodinger equation. Each of these has similarities, but also introduces some statistical arguments to ultimately obtain an average kinetic energy expression based on derivatives of classical density.

In (1), the Liouville and continuity equations are used:

$$d/dt \text{ partial } d(x,t) + d/dx \text{ partial } (p(x,t)/m \ d(x,t)) = 0 \quad ((1))$$

$$d/dt \text{ partial } (p(x,t) \ d(x,t)) + 1/m \ \text{Integral } pp \ F(p,x,t) \ dp + dV/dx \ \text{partial}, \ d(x,t) = 0 \quad ((2))$$

The idea is to ultimately pull d/dx out from all terms (e.g. dV/dx) which leaves essentially a conservation of energy equation. This strategy seems to be used in all such Liouville-continuity equation approaches. As a result, one has terms such as:

$$dp(x,t)/dt \text{ partial and } d/dx p(x,t)p(x,t)/2m \quad ((3))$$

As well as an Integral $dp \text{ pp } F(p,x,t)$ term. Note: p is a variable which may fluctuate and $p(x,t)$ is a specific trajectory. The two are not the same in (1).

The point we wish to make is that (1) does two fundamental things:

- A) The authors develop a statistical approach to solving Integral $pp F(p,x,t)$ using an axiom linking the variance of p and x together with a Boltzmann $\exp(-\text{Entropy}/T)$ expression for the probability of x . In short, this represents a main contribution to (1) and is directly linked to developing an expression for average kinetic energy for a density $d(x,t)$ such that $d/dx d(x,t)$ is not 0.
- B) At the same time, (1) assumes that $p(x,t) = dS(x,t) / dx \text{ partial}$ and this later also implies that $dS/dt \text{ partial} = -E$.

The main point we wish to make is that the assumption B means $dp(x,t)/dt \text{ partial} = d/x d/dt S$ and $dS/dt \text{ partial} = -E$ in the energy continuity equation and $p(x,t)p(x,t) = dS/dx dS/dx \text{ partial}$. This leads to the following form for $S(x,t)$ for a bound state with P being the center of mass momentum:

$$S(x,t) = -Et + Px \quad ((4))$$

If ((4)) applies to the center-of-mass, it should also apply to a free particle. We note that $-Et+Px$ is a Lorentz invariant as well as the relativistic and nonrelativistic classical action for $v=x/t$.

We suggest that one is already using an operator approach to obtain values of E and P . $d/dt \text{ partial}$ and $d/dx \text{ partial}$ already appear in the Liouville-continuity statistical equations and one wished to pull conservation of energy from these forcing one to introduce $p(x,t) = dS(x,t)/dx \text{ partial}$.

Given the form ((4)), one may write the eigenfunction $\exp(-iEt+ipx)$ such that $id/dt \text{ partial}$ and $-id/dx \text{ partial}$ return E and p . This function may be thought of as a probability, e.g.

$$P \text{ average} = p \exp(-iEt+ipx) / \exp(-iEt+ipx) \quad ((5))$$

This suggests that in the case of $V(x)$, one has a statistical recipe (independent of assumption (A) of (1) or the other assumptions in other papers). In particular:

$$KE_{ave}(x) = \{ \text{Sum over } p \ a(p) \ pp/2m \ \exp(ipx) \} / \{ \text{Sumover } p \ a(p)\exp(ipx) \} \quad ((6))$$

If one writes $W = \text{Sum over } p \ a(p)\exp(ipx)$, then for a bound state:

$$-1/2m \frac{d}{dx} \frac{dW}{dx} + V(x) = E_n \quad ((7))$$

One needs no extra statistical assumptions and axioms as presented in (1) (although ultimately (1) does arrive at ((7))).

We also note that in (1), a mathematical change of variables is introduced as:

$$W(x) = \sqrt{d(x,t)} \exp(i S(x,t)) \quad ((8))$$

In the case of a free particle, $d(x,t) = 1/\sqrt{L}$ so $\exp(iS(x,t)/\sqrt{L})$ multiplied by its conjugate actually yields $d(x,t)$. In (1), such a connection is not mentioned. We suggest that this independently leads to the idea of $W(x) = \text{Sum over } p \ a(p) \exp(ipx)$ such that $d(x,t) = W^*(x,t)W(x,t)$.

Conclusion

In conclusion, many papers in the literature use classical Liouville-continuity equation theory to derive the Schrodinger equation. Each of these introduces special statistical conditions in order to obtain an average kinetic energy term based on d/dx partial derivatives of the classical density, $d(x,t)$. At the same time, these approaches all seem to create an energy continuity equation from the combined Liouville -continuity equation such that:

$$\frac{d}{dt} \text{partial } S(x,t) = -E \text{ and } \frac{d}{dx} \text{partial } S(x,t) = p(x,t) \quad ((9))$$

This implies that $S = -Et + px$ where E is the bound state energy and p , the cm momentum.

This suggests that $-Et + px$ should also hold for a free particle and that one is applying d/dt partial and d/dx partial to a function of x,t to obtain E and p .

We suggest that one may write the math function $\exp(-iEt + ipx)$ and use this as a probability function and obtain an expression for average kinetic energy ((6)) without using any of the special statistical arguments given in (1) or other papers. In this way, one directly obtains the Schrodinger time-independent equation.

We also note that these approaches define $W(x,t) = (\text{wavefunction}) = \sqrt{d(x,t)} \exp(i S(x,t))$. For a free particle with $L=1$, $d(x,t) = 1$ so $\exp(iS)$ multiplied by its conjugate actually represents $d(x,t)$. One could apply this to create $W(x) = \text{sum over } p \ a(p)\exp(ipx)$ such that $d(x,t) = W(x)W(x)$ which is what these papers use. This approach, however, again leads to $\exp(ipx)$ as a probability for calculating average KE.

In other words, we argue that the various different statistical arguments used in different papers to obtain an expression for what becomes an average kinetic energy term in the Liouville equation actually follow from $\exp(ipx)$ used as a probability. This bypasses all of these arguments and is essentially introduced a priori in these approaches when they assume that $p(x,t) = dS(x,t)/dx$ partial and also that $-E = dS/dt$ partial. In other words, what appears to be a

minor assumption in the approaches seems to be actually the introduction of quantum mechanics, so one could proceed directly to the Schrodinger equation even without any use of the Liouville or continuity equations. One only needs to use: $KE_{ave}(x) + V(x) = E$.

References

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